

“Exposure Assessment in Lead”

ImproRisk Scientific Report

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1 Summary

Lead occurs primarily in the inorganic form in the environment. Human exposure is mainly via food and water, with some via air, dust and soil. Lead is considered to be responsible for developmental neurotoxicity in young children and cardiovascular effects and nephrotoxicity in adults.

In the current report the dietary exposure of the target population is studied using ImproRisk model v.0.3.2. The aim of this risk assessment study was to estimate the dietary Lead intake of the population in Cyprus, to carry out the necessary risk characterization and to calculate the contribution rate of the major food groups to the Lead exposure.

Mean dietary Lead exposure of the Cypriot population was calculated as 0.17 and 0.37 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ b.w./day for mean and high consumers, respectively. Current exposure levels of Cypriot population are not of health concern with regards to developmental neurotoxicity, nephrotoxicity and cardiovascular effects.

There was no significant difference in Lead intake between geographical areas and genders. It was found that infants, toddlers and other children had higher exposure values due to their lower body weight and their consumption habits.

In general, almost all food categories contributed to Lead exposure to Lead. Tomatoes, potatoes, cattle milk, poultry fresh meat, pig fresh meat and cereal flakes were the food categories with the highest contribution to the Lead intake.

2 Introduction

Lead is an environmental contaminant that occurs naturally and, to a greater extent, from anthropogenic activities such as mining and smelting and battery manufacturing. Lead is a metal that occurs in organic and inorganic forms; the latter predominates in the environment. Control measures have been taken to regulate lead in paint, petrol, food cans and pipes in Europe since the 1970s. Human exposure to lead can occur via food, water, air, soil and dust. Food is the major source of exposure to lead. The primary techniques for analysing lead in food samples are based on atomic absorption spectrometry, atomic emission spectrometry and mass spectrometry after digestion of organic material with concentrated acids.

The CONTAM Panel of EFS identified developmental neurotoxicity in young children and cardiovascular effects and nephrotoxicity in adults as potential critical adverse effects of lead. In order to carry out risk characterisation, the Margin of Exposure (MOE) approach is applied. MOE is calculated as the Benchmark Dose Level (BMDL) value divided by the respective intake. EFSA has selected BMDL₀₁ value of 0.50 µg/kg b.w. per day for developmental neurotoxicity, effects on systolic blood pressure BMDL₀₁ value of 1.50 µg/kg b.w. per day and BMDL₁₀ value of 0.63 µg/kg b.w. per day effects on prevalence of chronic kidney disease.

2.1 Background

2.2 Terms of Reference

The aim of this risk assessment study was to estimate the dietary Lead intake of the population in Cyprus, to carry out the necessary risk characterization and to calculate the contribution rate of the major food groups to the Lead exposure. Lead is considered to be responsible for developmental neurotoxicity in young children and cardiovascular effects and nephrotoxicity in adults.

3 Data and Methodology

3.1 Occurrence data

Lead occurrence data in food were extracted from LIMS for the years 2008-2020. For results below LOD, EFSA's assumption was applied. Occurrence results below the LOD were set to zero for the Low-bound scenario, half the LOD for the Middle-bound scenario and LOD for the Upper-bound scenario. Dilution factors were applied in order to estimate concentrations for different coffee beverages, tea beverages and liquid children and infant milk. The aggregated occurrence dataset contained 224 food items.

3.2 Consumption data

Food consumption data were obtained from the EUMenu project funded by EFSA and the dietary survey was carried out in the years 2014-2018. The consumption data was the result of a survey of 1661 participants (male and female). The survey covered all five cities of Cyprus, rural and urban regions, and also all days of the week and the four seasons. The population classes and the number of participants in each class were: [a] infants: 3-11 months (269), [b] toddlers: 12-35 months (279), [c] other children: 3-9 years (300), [d] adolescents: 10-17 years (274), [e] adults: 18-64 years (275) and [f] elderly: 65-74 years (264). The consumption dataset contained 82921 occasions.

3.3 Food classification

Consumption and occurrence data were both codified according to the FoodEx2 classification system developed by EFSA. At the moment of the generation of the present report the MTX catalogue version 13.1 was applied.

3.4 Methodologies

3.4.1 Chronic dietary exposure

Dietary exposure was assessed at individual level by multiplying the average daily consumption of each food with the corresponding mean occurrence estimated for Lead summing up the respective intakes throughout the diet and finally dividing the results by the individual's body weight.

3.4.2 Dietary exposure assessment model

Dietary exposure assessment was performed using ImproRisk model version 0.3.2

4 Dietary Exposure Assessment

Table 4.1 presents the substance information.

Table 4.1: Substance information

key	
Chemical Substance	Lead
Substance Category	Contaminant
Reference value	0.63 µg/Kg b.w. per day
Type of reference value	Benchmark Dose Level (BMDL)

Table 4.2 presents the exposure statistics.

Table 4.2: Summary exposure statistics of Lead

Scenario			
key	LB (µg/Kg b.w. per day)	MB (µg/Kg b.w. per day)	UB (µg/Kg b.w. per day)
Min	0.02	0.028	0.035
Max	1.909	1.931	1.953
Mean	0.136	0.17	0.205
SD	0.127	0.14	0.155
P25	0.078	0.103	0.124
Median	0.109	0.138	0.168
P75	0.153	0.196	0.238
P95	0.304	0.371	0.44
MoE ¹	4.64	3.70	3.07
MoE ²	11.05	8.81	7.31
MoE ³	3.69	2.94	2.44

* MoE : Margin of Exposure, 1: Nephrotoxicity, 2: Cardiovascular effects, 3: Developmental neurotoxicity

Mean and 95th percentile exposure were calculated as 0.17 and 0.37 µg/kg b.w. per day (Table 4.2). The above values are lower than the corresponding exposure estimates, calculated by EFSA.

MOEs for developmental neurotoxicity (BMDL of 0.5 µg/Kg b.w. per day), nephrotoxicity (BMDL of 0.63 µg/Kg b.w. per day) and cardiovascular effects (BMDL of 1.5 µg/Kg b.w. per day) obtained for the current exposure to Lead (Table 4.2) are all above 1, which is considered a safety margin for no health concern.

4.1 Distribution of exposure

Probability distribution

Figure 4.1 shows the probability distribution of the exposure.

Figure 4.1: Probability distribution of exposure at the MB scenario

Figure 4.1 shows the distribution of exposure of the Cypriot population based on mean occurrence. It can be shown that more than 98% of the population was exposed to Lead less than 0.5 µg/Kg bw per day.

Cumulative distribution

Figure 4.2 shows the cumulative distribution of exposure.

Figure 4.2: Cumulative distribution of exposure at the MB scenario

4.2 Mean Exposure at the MB by Gender

Table 4.3: Summary exposure statistics Gender at MB scenario.

Gender	Min	Max	Mean	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	MoE
FEMALE	0.028	1.931	0.165	0.162	0.096	0.133	0.185	0.348	3.827
MALE	0.039	1.227	0.176	0.113	0.106	0.150	0.210	0.385	3.576

Table 4.3 and Figure 4.3 shows that there is no significant difference between the two genders meaning same food consumption habits for male and female subjects.

Figure 4.3: Mean Exposure by Gender at MB scenario.

4.3 Mean Exposure at the MB by Area

Table 4.4: Summary exposure statistics by Area at MB scenario.

Area	Min	Max	Mean	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	MoE
Ammochostos	0.050	1.336	0.157	0.106	0.085	0.138	0.196	0.323	4.013
Larnaka	0.028	1.227	0.150	0.104	0.095	0.123	0.174	0.334	4.187
Lefkosia	0.028	1.267	0.175	0.114	0.101	0.145	0.215	0.391	3.592
Lemesos	0.038	1.931	0.192	0.209	0.109	0.142	0.207	0.390	3.290
Pafos	0.043	1.054	0.155	0.084	0.113	0.138	0.185	0.262	4.062

Figure 4.4: Mean Exposure by Area at MB scenario.

4.4 Mean Exposure at the MB by Population Class

Table 4.5: Summary exposure statistics by Population Class at MB scenario.

Population class	Min	Max	Mean	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	MoE
Adolescents	0.050	0.475	0.187	0.077	0.138	0.168	0.226	0.334	3.374
Adults	0.028	1.931	0.142	0.123	0.096	0.129	0.170	0.244	4.422
Elderly	0.028	1.196	0.132	0.091	0.085	0.117	0.155	0.247	4.778
Infants	0.062	1.492	0.476	0.253	0.310	0.465	0.604	0.967	1.324
Other children	0.067	0.799	0.308	0.126	0.219	0.290	0.377	0.560	2.046
Toddlers	0.107	1.227	0.435	0.176	0.307	0.414	0.537	0.728	1.447

In Figure 4.5 the exposure of each population class is shown. It was found that infants, toddlers and other children had two or three times higher exposure than adults due to their lower body weight. Although, infants and toddlers may consume less food contaminated with Lead, they showed high exposure because they have the lowest body weight. Although infants, toddlers and other children had much higher exposures than the other population

classes, MOE was more than 1, indicating that the health risk of the current intake level is acceptable.

Figure 4.5: Mean Exposure by Population Class at MB scenario.

4.5 Mean Exposure at the MB scenario by [population class and area]

Figures 4.6 illustrate the mean exposure to Lead by population class and geographical area. It was found that there is no significant difference between the geographical areas in all population classes. The exposure seems to be independent of the geographical area. This is because the population in Cyprus has the same food consumption habits and the foodstuffs that are contaminated by Lead are consumed by all population classes.

Mean Lead exposure (MB scenario)

Across Area and Population class

Figure 4.6: Cross Plot

4.6 Contributions of different food groups to the dietary exposure

The contribution of each main food group to the total Lead exposure is shown in Figure 4.7. Tomatoes (10.4%), potatoes (8.2%), cattle milk (5.7%), poultry fresh meat (4.4%), pig fresh meat (4.3%) and cereal flakes (4.0%) were the food categories with the highest contribution to the Lead intake. It was obtained that in general exposure to Lead is uniformly distributed to all food categories with the exception of one or two food groups that are consumed in higher amounts and by all population groups.

Figure 4.7 shows the contribution of food items at FoodEx Level 4

Figure 4.7: Contribution to the Lead Total Exposure MB.

Table 4.6: Contribution to the Lead Total Exposure (MB). Food items at FoodEx2 Level 4 with greater than 1% contribution

Level1	Level2	Level3	Level4	Contribution
Grains and grain-based products	Cereals and cereal primary derivatives	Cereal grains (and cereal-like grains)	Rice and similar-	1.61%
Grains and grain-based products	Cereals and cereal primary derivatives	Cereal and cereal-like flours	Wheat flour	1.14%

Level1	Level2	Level3	Level4	Contribution
Grains and grain-based products	Fine bakery wares	Biscuits	Biscuit with inclusions, filling or coating	1.04%
Grains and grain-based products	Breakfast cereals	Processed and mixed breakfast cereals	Cereal flakes and similar	3.99%
Grains and grain-based products	Pasta, doughs and similar products	Pasta and similar products	Pasta, plain (not stuffed), uncooked	1.43%
Vegetables and vegetable products	Bulb vegetables	Onions and similar-	Onions	3.38%
Vegetables and vegetable products	Fruiting vegetables	Solanacea	Tomatoes and similar-	10.39%
Vegetables and vegetable products	Leafy vegetables	Lettuces and salad plants	Lettuces and similar-	2.31%
Vegetables and vegetable products	Herbs and edible flowers	Aromatic herbs	Celery leaves and similar-	3.47%
Vegetables and vegetable products	Herbs and edible flowers	Aromatic herbs	Basils and mints	2.68%
Starchy roots or tubers and products thereof, sugar plants	Starchy roots and tubers	Potatoes and similar-	Potatoes	8.19%
Fruit and fruit products	Fruit used as fruit	Pome fruits	Apples and similar-	3.13%
Fruit and fruit products	Fruit used as fruit	Miscellaneous fruits with inedible peel, large	Bananas and similar-	2.48%
Meat and meat products	Mammals and birds meat	Mammals meat	Pig fresh meat	4.27%
Meat and meat products	Mammals and birds meat	Birds meat	Poultry fresh meat (muscle meat)	4.38%
Milk and dairy products	Milk, whey and cream	Milk	Cattle milk	5.65%
Milk and dairy products	Milk, whey and cream	Milk	Other milks	1.16%

5 Uncertainties

The evaluation of the uncertainties in the exposure assessment of Lead has been performed following the guidance of the Opinion of the Scientific Committee related to Uncertainties in Dietary Exposure Assessment. Table 5.1 presents a summary of uncertainties, highlighting the main sources of uncertainty and providing an estimate whether each source of uncertainty is likely to lead to an over- or under-estimation of the calculated dietary exposure.

Table 5.1: Summary of qualitative evaluation of the impact of uncertainties on the dietary exposure to Lead.

Sources of uncertainty	Direction ¹
Different time frame between concentration data and consumption data	+/-
Long-term (chronic) exposure assessed from few days of consumption	+
Measurement error in amounts of food consumed	+/-
Measurement error in individual body weights	+/-
Assumptions taken into account for the preparation of occurrence data	+/-
Level up approach matching in the FoodEx2 exposure hierarchy for the calculation of the exposure	+

¹ + = uncertainty with potential to cause over-estimation of exposure; - = uncertainty with potential to cause under-estimation of exposure

A number of uncertainties can be identified regarding the selection of parameters, such as Lead concentration levels in foodstuffs and consumption data.

The uncertainty related to the representativeness of the occurrence data for certain food commodities with respect to the number of samples is taken into account. Given the fact that the analytical results were generated with an ICP-MS method in an accredited laboratory, this adds only slightly to the uncertainty of the analytical results.

Some potentially important extrapolation uncertainties arise since an individual survey of food consumption is used to estimate dietary exposure over a timescale longer than the survey duration. Remaining uncertainties relate to the measurement error in amounts of consumed foodstuffs and individual body weights.

In ImproRisk occurrence and consumption data matching for the calculation of the exposure is performed based on a level up approach matching in the FoodEx2 exposure hierarchy, which may lead to overestimation of the exposure.

Furthermore, several assumption taken into account in the preparation of the occurrence (data from EFSA, dilution factors, aggregation) data may lead to some uncertainties.

6 Conclusions

Mean dietary Lead exposure of the Cypriot population was calculated as 0.17 and 0.37 µg/kg b.w./day for mean and high consumers, respectively. Current exposure levels of Cypriot population are not of health concern with regards to developmental neurotoxicity, nephrotoxicity and cardiovascular effects.

There was no significant difference in Lead intake between geographical areas and genders. It was found that infants, toddlers and other children had higher exposure values due to their lower body weight and their consumption habits.

In general, almost all food categories contributed to Lead exposure to Lead. Tomatoes (10.4%), potatoes (8.2%), cattle milk (5.7%), poultry fresh meat (4.4%), pig fresh meat (4.3%) and cereal flakes (4.0%) were the food categories with the highest contribution to the Lead intake.

7 References

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8 Abbreviations

Table 8.1: Abbreviations

Key	Description
BMDL	Benchmark dose lower limit (lower bound of benchmark dose interval)

Key	Description
b.w.	Body weight
LB	Lower bound
LOD	Limit of detection
MB	Middle bound
MoE	Margin of exposure
SD	Standard deviation
P25	25th percentile
P75	75th percentile
P95	95th percentile
UB	Upper bound
wcoeff	Weight coefficient

9 Appendices